

Short name	Lack of incentives for BECCS and DAC	Long name	No policy instrument supporting BECCS or DAC in the EU
Geographical scope	EU member states		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>The EU ETS is the primary policy instrument to generate revenue for CC(U)S activities in EU member states. However, as biogenic carbon is counted as climate neutral in the ETS any carbon captured and stored from biogenic sources does not generate a monetizable result under the ETS. These CO₂ volumes are currently not accounted for in any other policy instrument either. The ETS Directive Article 24 provides for an option for MS to include other volumes and activities than those directly comprised by the directive on a case by case basis, which results in an option for value chains to be deployed and BECCS or DAC to be incentivized under the ETS scheme.</p> <p>Biomass based CC(U)S installations may be piloted through direct funding from the Innovation fund, however, they lack a pathway for long-term viability and are thus not properly incentivized. The same is true for installations that have mixed streams of carbon from fossil (or mineral in case of cement) and biomass origin.</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	There is presently no incentivization for the operation of CC(U)S projects based on biomass or DAC. The case by case inclusion of the CO ₂ volumes stemming from biomass or DAC further cases lack of predictability, delays and the need for increased resources to deploy such value chains, in e.g. the permitting and MRV process.		
Other issues this affects	Incentivization of CC(U)S, MRV		
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Biogas Association. (2022). Biogenic CO₂ from the biogas industry: A mature business opportunity to enhance sustainable carbon cycles and untap the circularity and climate benefits of biogas production. Retrieved from https://european-biogas.eu/publications/biogenic-co2-from-the-biogas-industry/ • Zero Emissions Platform. (2021). ZEP position paper on EU ETS. Retrieved from https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/wp-content/uploads/ZEP-position-paper-on-EU-ETS.pdf 		